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Phenotypic and Genotypic Correlation Coefficients and Path Coefficient Analysis Studies of Upland Cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.)

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Received Date: 21-Jan-2020

Accepted Date: 25-Feb-2020

Published Date: 30-April-2020

Abstract

the present study contained 16 testing genotypes that were laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with four replications at Cotton Research Station, Dera Ismail Khan, Pakistan with an objective of determining association of traits. Days to emergence, number of sympodial branches plant⁻¹, number of nodes to first fruiting branch, Plant height, boll number plant⁻¹, boll weight, seed cotton yield plot⁻¹, Seed cotton yield ha⁻¹, ginning percentage, lint yield plot⁻¹ and ha⁻¹, hundred seed weight, micronaire, upper half mean length, short fiber content, fiber Strength, degree of reflectance and yellowness had showed significance difference at (p=0.05) and their genetic variability was further calculated. Associations among various traits at genotypic and phenotypic level showed that lint yield ha⁻¹ was positively associated with seed cotton yield, boll number per plant and ginning percentage and micronaire. Path coefficient analysis at phenotypic and genotypic level for agronomic traits revealed that seed cotton yield ha⁻¹ and ginning percentage were the most important traits in determining lint yield ha⁻¹. These traits exerted the highest positive direct effect on lint yield ha⁻¹. Path coefficient analysis of quality traits at phenotypic level revealed that upper half mean length had showed the highest direct positive effect on fiber strength followed by short fiber content and fiber uniformity, respectively. The path coefficient analysis for genotypic level of fiber quality traits had showed upper half mean length, fiber uniformity and degree of reflectance had a direct positive effect on fiber strength

Key words: correlation, direct effect, indirect effect, path coefficients, variability

INTRODUCTION

Correlations and Path Coefficients

Correlation coefficients

Correlation among different agronomic and morphological characters is an important aspect for better planning of selection programs and is also helpful in determining the components of complex trait like yield. In selection process for crop improvement, knowledge of association of various characters is the most important tool (Desai *et al.*, 1994).

The relationship between yield and its components may be due to genetic linkage, pleiotropic or developmental causes. Significant genetic correlation coefficient between two characters does not always indicate presence of linkage between them. Two characters having a common physiological or biochemical chain may also show such genetic correlation (Hohenboken, 1985).

The correlation and path analysis studies are important assets to the breeder, especially in case of fiber crops like cotton, where in quantity and quality traits both are important. The information on the nature and magnitude of variability and correlation in a population owing to genetic and non-genetic factor is one of the prerequisites in any hybridization programme for selecting parents with desirable characters. In selection

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process for crop improvement, knowledge of association of various characters is the most important tool. Seed cotton is determined by many yield components and associated with many other traits, so knowing these associations and modifying these components may lead to a higher success rate in yield improvement.

Higher genotypic correlations than phenotypic ones might be due to modifying or masking effect of environment in the expression of these characters under study as explained by Nandpuriet *et al.*, (1973). Johnson *et al.*, (1955) also reported that higher genotypic correlation than phenotypic correlation indicated an inherent association between various characters.

Seed cotton yield was reported to have a significant positive correlation with bolls per plant, boll weight, lint yield, lint percent, lint index, and seed per boll (Desalegn *et al.*, 2009; Khan *et al.*, 2010). One of the major setbacks in improvement has been the negative linkages between yield and fiber properties. Improving seed cotton yield while simultaneously maintaining fiber properties has been quite a challenge because of these negative associations. However, some studies have found a significant positive correlation between seed cotton yield and fiber strength, and seed cotton yield and fiber fineness (Azhare *et al.*, 2004). Exploring genetic diversity within *G. hirsutum* seems like an attractive option to break the negative linkages with seed cotton yield. Lint yield was reported to have highly significant positive correlation with seed cotton yield, bolls per plant, lint percent, lint index, seed per boll, and non-significant correlations with boll weight, and a negative correlation with seed index (Desalegn *et al.*, 2009; Percy *et al.*, 2006).

One of the major challenges with improving fiber length is its negative correlation with lint yield (Campbell *et al.*, 2012). However, the strength of negative correlation between fiber length and lint yield has been reduced through breeding efforts in Pee Dee germplasm (Campbell *et al.*, 2011, 2012, 2013). Reports indicate fiber length and fiber strength are positively correlated, implying improving fiber length also improves fiber strength (Lu and Myers, 2011; Ulloa, 2006).

Path coefficient

The association of characters as determined by the simple correlation coefficient may not provide an exact representation of the relationship between yield and yield attributes. In contrast, path coefficient analysis permits a critical examination of specific direct and indirect effects of characters and measures the relative importance of each of them in determining the ultimate goal yield.

But the correlation alone cannot prove the exact picture of the relative importance of direct and indirect influences of each of the component characters towards yield. So, the character association is further analyzed through path coefficient. The adequate knowledge of interrelationship among various traits and the practices of unilateral selection for agronomic traits frequently end up in retrograde or less than an optimum result in plant breeding (Bhatt, 1973).

Path coefficient analysis developed by Wright in 1921 and by Dewey and Lu in 1959 measures the magnitude of direct and indirect contribution of the component characters to a complex character and has defined as a standardized regression coefficient which splits the correlation coefficient into direct and indirect effects (Singh, 2007; Acquah, 2007). Unlike correlation coefficient which measures the extent of relationship between two variables which may be due to a third factor (Sadeghi *et al.*, 2011), path analysis shows the cause and effect relationship between dependent and independent variables to entangle the nature of relationship between the variables (Sigramappa *et al.*, 2008). If the correlation between the independent and dependent variables due to direct effect of the independent variable, it reflects the true relationship between them and selection can be practiced for the independent character in order to improve the dependent character (Singh, 2007).

Generally, to develop suitable varieties, it is important to understand the interrelationships among cotton lint yield and fiber quality yield related traits to design strategies for improvement of complex traits such as yield per unit area through indirect selections. This work may also initiate further studies on the correlation among traits of existing germplasm of upland cotton at WARC. Therefore, the present study was conducted with the objectives of determining the phenotypic and genotypic correlations between various traits of cotton and

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identifying traits that can be used as indirect selection to improve seed cotton yield and lint yield. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Description of the testing Site

The study was conducted at Cotton Research Station, Pakistan Central Cotton Committee, Multan during 2016 cropping season (May to November, 2016). Pakistan (31°49' N, 70°55' E, 165 m above sea level). The soil of the experimental site is hyperthermic and Typic Torrifuvents (Soil Survey Staff 2009). It is moderately saline; less fertile than the typical cotton belt in Punjab, Pakistan, having relatively high silt and clay content; and needs irrigation for crop production. The climatic data were obtained from the agro-meteorological station in D.I. Khan near the experimental site. D.I.Khan has a typical arid climate with hotdry summers, moderate rain during monsoon season, and cold winter.

Experimental Materials

Fourteen *Gossypium hirsutum*F₅ lines obtained from a cross between Deltapine-90 and Delcerowere used for the study along with the two parents (Table 1).

Table 1. List of cotton genotypes used in the study and their pedigree

TreatmentNo	Treatment code	Treatments/pedigrees
1	A	Delcero X Deltapine-90 #F5-5-3-2-1-1
2	B	Delcero X Deltapine-90 #F5-5-3-2-2-1
3	C	Delcero XDeltapine-90 #F5-5-3-2-2-Bulk
4	D	Delcero XDeltapine-90 #F5-5-3-3-1-1
5	E	Delcero XDeltapine-90 #F5-5-3-3-1-2
6	F	Delcero X Deltapine-90 #F5-5-4-2-1-Bulk
7	G	Delcero X Deltapine-90 #F5-5-4-2-2-1
8	H	Delcero X Deltapine-90 #F5-5-4-2-3-2
9	I	Delcero X Deltapine-90 #F5-5-4-2-3-3
10	J	Delcero X Deltapine-90 #F5-5-4-2-3-Bulk
11	K	Delcero X Deltapine-90 #F5-5-4-3-1-Bulk
12	L	Delcero XDeltapine-90 #F5-5-4-3-2-1
13	M	Delcero X Deltapine-90 #F5-5-4-3-3-Bulk
14	N	Delcero XDeltapine-90 #F5-5-7-1-1-1
15	O	Deltapine-90 (Parental line)
16	P	Delcero (Parental line)

Experimental Design and Layout

The experiment was laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with four replications. Each treatment had five rows, each five meters long with spacing of 90 cm between rows and 20cm between plants. The plot size was 5 x 5m x 0.9m =22.5m². Net plot size was 3 rows x 5m x 0.9m=13.5 m².

Statistical Analysis

Analysis of covariance

ANCOVA (Analysis of Covariance) was calculated using the following model.

Table 2. Analysis of covariance

Source of variation	d.f	Mscp	Expected covariances
Block (Rep)	b-1	MSCP _{bxy}	
Genotypes	(g-1)	MSCP _{Gxy}	$\sigma^2e_{xy} + r \sigma^2g_{xy}$
Error	(g-1)(b-1)	MSCP _{exy}	σ^2e_{xy}
Total	gb-1		

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d.f= degree of freedom, r= replication, b=block

MSCP_{bxy}=mean sum of cross productof blocks for variable x and y

MSCP_{Gxy} = mean sum of cross productof genotypes for variable x and y

MSCP_{exy}=mean sum of cross productof error for variable x and y

σ^2_{exy} =MSCP_{exy} = environmental covariance between trait x and y

$$\text{Genotypic covariance } (\sigma^2_{gxy}) = \frac{(\text{MSCPG}_{xy} - \text{MSCP}_{exy})}{r}$$

Environmental covariance between traits x and y (σ^2_{exy}) = MSCP_{exy}

$$\text{Phenotypic covariance } (\sigma^2_{pxy}) = \frac{(\sigma^2_{gxy} + \sigma^2_{exy})}{r}$$

3.6.4. Phenotypic and genotypic correlations

Phenotypic correlation and genotypic correlations were computed following the method described by miller *et al.*(1985):

$$r_{pxy} = \frac{\sigma^2_{pxy}}{\sqrt{(\sigma^2_{px})(\sigma^2_{py})}}$$

$$r_{gxy} = \frac{\sigma^2_{gxy}}{\sqrt{(\sigma^2_{gx})(\sigma^2_{gy})}}$$

Where r is replication, r_{pxy} and r_{gxy} are phenotypic and genoytpic correlation coefficient, respectively; σ_{pxy} and σ_{gxy} are phenotypic covariance and genotypic covariance between character x and y, respectively; σ^2_{px} and σ^2_{gx} are phenotypic and genotypic variances for trait x; and σ^2_{py} and σ^2_{gy} are phenotypic and genotypic variances for the trait y respectively.

The coefficient of correlations at the phenotypic level have been tested for their significance with the Table for simple correlation coefficient using(g-2) degrees of freedom as indicated by Gomez and Gomez(1984) or using simple t-Table,

$$\text{Where } t = \frac{r_{pxy}\sqrt{(g-2)}}{\sqrt{(1-r_{pxy})}}$$

Where r_{pxy} is the phenotypic correlation coefficient and g the number of genotypes. The calculated t -value were compared with the t- tabulated at(g-2) degrees of freedom.

The genotypic correlation coefficient has been tested for its significance with the formula of Robertson(1959):

$$t = \frac{r_{gxy}}{SE_{r_{gxy}}}$$

Where r_{gxy} is the genotypic correlation coefficient and SE_{r_{gxy}} is the standard error of the genotypic correlation coefficient.

$$SE_{r_{gxy}} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{1 - r_{gxy}^2}{2h^2_x h^2_y}\right)}$$

h^2_x and h^2_y are the heritability for character x and y respectively. The calculated t-value for each genotypic correlation was tested against tabulated t at (g-2) degree of freedom.

Path coefficient analysis

Path coefficient Analysis has been undergone for parameters to partition the correlation coefficient to direct and indirect effects of the components on lint cotton yield and fiber strength as illustrated by Dewey and Lu (1959).

The formula:-

$$r_{ij} = p_{ij} + \sum r_{ik} p_{kj}$$

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where, r_{ij} = Mutual association between the independent character (i) and dependent character (j) as measured by the correlation coefficient, p_{ij} = components of direct effects of the independent character (i) on the dependent character (j) as measured by the path coefficient and $\sum r_{ik}p_{kj}$ = summation of components of indirect effect of a given independent character (i) on the given independent character (j) via all other independent characters (k)

The residual effect (h) was estimated by the following formula:

$$h = \sqrt{(1 - R^2)}; \text{ where } R^2 = \sum p_{ij}r_{ij}$$

P_{ij} = components of direct effects of the independent character (i) on dependent character (i) as measured by the path coefficient.

r_{ij} = Mutual association between the dependent and independent character (i) and dependent character (j) as measured by the correlation coefficient.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Phenotypic and Genotypic Associations among Characters

Quantitative traits

Correlation of lint yield and yield related traits

In this study, the genotypic and phenotypic correlation coefficients between yield and yield contributing characters are discussed below at table 3. It appears that in most of the cases the genotypic correlation values were higher than their corresponding phenotypic values. This suggests that there were strong inherent relationship between the traits. Lint yield ha^{-1} results revealed strong positive correlation with seed cotton yield ha^{-1} ($r_{ph} = 0.968$ and $r_g = 0.973$), boll number plant^{-1} ($r_{ph} = 0.926$ and $r_g = 1.00$), ginning percentage ($r_{ph} = 0.661$ and $r_g = 0.85$), short fiber content ($r_{ph} = 0.691$ and $r_g = 1.00$) and degree of reflectance ($r_{ph} = 0.667$ and $r_g = 1.00$) at both phenotypic and genotypic level indicating the increase in lint yield mainly because of the increase in one or more of the above characters.

Lint yield ha^{-1} had positive association with number of sympodial branches ($r_{ph} = 0.572$ and $r_g = 0.813$), number of nodes to first fruiting branch ($r_{ph} = 0.389$ and $r_g = 0.677$), plant height ($r_{ph} = 0.347$ and $r_g = 0.276$), micronaire ($r_{ph} = 0.448$ and $r_g = 0.665$), yellowness ($r_{ph} = 0.221$ and $r_g = 0.408$) at both phenotypic and genotypic level. This study agrees with the findings of Azharet *et al.* (2004), who found indicated a significant positive correlation between lint yield and fiber fineness.

In contrast lint yield ha^{-1} exhibited negative correlation with days to emergence ($r_{ph} = -0.342$ and $r_g = -0.402$), boll weight ($r_{ph} = -0.463$ and $r_g = -0.712$), hundred seed weight ($r_{ph} = -0.622$ and $r_g = -0.817$), fiber strength ($r_{ph} = -0.555$ and $r_g = -0.724$), upper half mean length ($r_{ph} = -0.284$ and $r_g = -0.386$) and length uniformity ($r_{ph} = -0.460$ and $r_g = -0.782$) at both phenotypic and genotypic level. The breeder must be very careful while selecting predominantly one or more of these traits which may result in lint yield decline. Because these traits had negatively correlated with lint yield and cannot be used as positive selection parameters to increase lint yield per unit area. Lint cotton yield was not increased together with the main fiber quality traits because of having negative correlation. The result agrees with Campbell *et al.* (2011, 2012 and 2013), who also worked with cotton and found that fiber strength negatively correlated with lint yield.

Generally, in this study, positive genotypic and phenotypic correlations were observed between number of sympodial branches, plant height, number of nodes to first fruiting branch, boll number plant^{-1} , seed cotton yield ha^{-1} , ginning percentage, short fiber content and degree of reflectance, micronaire and yellowness with lint yield, which is considerably significant to breeders because component breeding would be very effective under such situation. Selection for these traits might be essential in involving high yielding varieties of upland cotton.

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The negative associations of lint yield with days to emergence, boll weight, hundred seed weight, upper half mean length and strength at both phenotypic and genotypic level justified that lint yield might not be improved simultaneously with main physical quality traits at both phenotypic and genetic level of correlation.

Table 3. Phenotypic and genotypic correlation coefficients of lint yield and related traits

Traits	LHA	DTE	SYM	NFFB	PLH	BOP	BOW	SHA	GP	HSW
LHA	1	-0.402	0.813*	0.677	0.276	1.00**	-0.712	0.973**	0.85**	-0.817*
DTE	-0.342	1	-0.156	-0.270	-0.158	-0.305	0.692	-0.361	-0.429	0.430
SYM	0.572*	-0.119	1	0.254	0.398	0.720	-0.103	0.964**	0.278	-0.129
NFFB	0.389	-0.197	0.175	1	0.805*	0.632	-0.453	0.607	0.606	-0.283
PLH	0.347	-0.186	0.433*	0.565*	1	0.458	0.020	0.303	0.111	0.243
BOP	0.926**	-0.272	0.627**	0.460	0.49*	1	-0.644	1.00**	0.73*	-0.683
BOW	-0.463*	0.464*	-0.019	-0.330	0.137	-0.492*	1	-0.577	-0.891**	0.93**
SHA	0.968**	-0.317	0.628**	0.308	0.405	0.903**	-0.297	1	0.707	-0.688
GP	0.661**	-0.284	0.157	0.421	-0.006	0.607**	-0.791**	0.453*	1	-0.971**
HSW	-0.622**	0.314	-0.111	-0.205	0.224	-0.588**	0.88**	-0.45*	-0.906**	1

*, ** are significance levels of p-value at 5%, 1% respectively and others are non-significant. LHA: lint yield ha⁻¹ (kg), DTE: Days to emergence, SYM:

number of sympodial Branch plant⁻¹, NFFB: number of nodes to first fruiting branch, PLH: plant height (cm), BOP: boll number plant⁻¹, BOW: boll weight (g), SHA:

seed cotton yield ha⁻¹ (kg), GP: ginning percentage, HSW: hundred seed weight (g)

Note that: Values below the diagonal are phenotypic correlation coefficients while values above the diagonal are genotypic correlation coefficients.

Fiber Quality traits

Micronaire which is one of the basic physical fiber quality, showed positive relation with lint cotton yield ($r_{ph} = 0.448$ and $r_g = 0.665$), short fiber content ($r_{ph} = 0.403$ and $r_g = 0.632$), and degree of reflectance ($r_{ph} = 0.382$ and $r_g = 0.638$). However, it had negative association with fiber strength ($r_{ph} = -0.763$ and $r_g = -0.862$), upper half mean length ($r_{ph} = -0.701$ and $r_g = -0.802$), length uniformity ($r_{ph} = -0.341$ and $r_g = -0.666$) and yellowness ($r_{ph} = -0.194$ and $r_g = -0.168$) (Table 4).

Upper half mean length is one of the main components of physical fiber quality parameters and it had positive correlation with fiber strength ($r_{ph} = 0.859$ and $r_g = 0.880$), length uniformity ($r_{ph} = 0.613$ and $r_g = 0.721$), and yellowness ($r_{ph} = 0.087$ and $r_g = 0.089$). In contrast this trait revealed negative association with short fiber content ($r_{ph} = -0.347$ and $r_g = -0.321$) (Table 4).

Fiber strength was positively correlated with length uniformity ($r_{ph} = 0.607$ and $r_g = 0.859$), but it exhibited negative correlation with short fiber content ($r_{ph} = -0.486$ and $r_g = -0.577$) and degree of reflectance ($r_{ph} = -0.481$ and $r_g = -0.634$) (Table 4).

Generally, the main components of fiber quality characters such as upper half mean length and fiber strength had highly significant and strong positive correlation at both phenotypic and genotypic level ($r_{ph} = 0.859$ and $r_g = 0.880$), respectively. This result agrees with Lu and Myers (2011) and Ulloa (2006) who reported that fiber length and fiber strength had positively correlated, implying improving fiber length also improves fiber strength. Upper half mean length and fiber strength revealed negative correlation with micronaire but all are highly demanded by garment and textile industry. These traits shall be improved through gene pyramiding crossing method to get novel genotypes.

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Table 4. Phenotypic and genotypic correlation coefficients of lint and lint quality traits

Traits	STR	LHA	MIC	UHML	UI	SF	RD	+b
STR	1	-0.724	-0.862**	0.880**	0.859**	-0.577	-0.634	-0.042
LHA	-0.555	1	0.665	-0.386	-0.782	1.00*	1.00**	0.408
MIC	-0.763**	0.448	1	-0.802**	-0.666	0.632	0.638	-0.168
UHML	0.859**	-0.284	-0.701*	1	0.721	-0.321	-0.162	0.089
UI	0.607*	-0.460	-0.341	0.613	1	-0.891**	-0.646	-0.143
SF	-0.486	0.691*	0.403	-0.347	-0.780*	1	1.00	-0.306
RD	-0.481	0.667*	0.382	-0.095	-0.343	0.683	1	-0.314
+b	-0.044	0.221	-0.194	0.087	-0.058	-0.193	-0.135	1

*, ** are significance levels of p-value at 5%, and 1%, respectively and ns= non significance. STR: fiber strength, LHA: lint yield ha⁻¹ (kg), MIC: micronaire (units), UHML: upper half mean length (mm), UNI: length uniformity(%), SF: short fiber content(%), RD: degree of reflectance, +b: yellowness

Path coefficient Analysis

Quantitative traits

Path coefficient analysis of phenotypic correlations

Path coefficient analysis of the phenotypic correlations revealed that seed cotton yield had the highest direct effect of 0.872 on lint yield (Table 5). This trait also had the highest positive phenotypic correlation (0.968) with cotton lint yield. The indirect effect of days to emergence (-0.002), number of sympodial branches (-0.0003), plant height (-0.003), boll number plant⁻¹ (-0.024), and hundred seed weight (-0.034), on lint yield via seed cotton yield were negative, although most of them were very small in absolute value (near zero). Seed cotton yield also had negative correlation with SYM and HSW. While selecting plants with high seed cotton yield, care should be taken not to select plants with many bolls and heavier (bigger) seeds. Plants with high ginning percentage (GP) can be emphasized since GP had relatively high positive indirect effect (0.152) on lint yield via seed cotton yield.

The variable that exerted the second highest positive direct effect on lint yield was ginning percentage (0.336); it also had positive phenotypic correlation (0.661) with lint yield. This trait that had negative indirect effect on lint yield via seed cotton yield except PLH i.e., DTE, SYM, BOP and HSW had negative indirect effect via ginning percentage. The highest positive indirect effect on lint yield via ginning percent was that of seed cotton yield. Plants with high ginning percentage and high seed cotton yield but with fewer BOP and smaller seeds should be selected.

Hundred seed weight (HSW) exerted relatively the third highest direct effect (0.075) on lint yield. However, HSW had negative phenotypic correlation (-0.622) with lint yield which resulted from the negative indirect effects of NFFB, PLH, BOW, SHA and GP, the indirect effects of SHA (-0.392) and GP (-0.304) being very large. HSW also had negative correlation with these two traits (-0.45 and -0.91, respectively). Although the direct effect of HSW on lint yield is positive, selection of genotypes with the highest HSW will lead to a decline in lint yield via seed cotton yield and ginning percentage. Genotypes with the highest SHA and GP but moderate seed size should be selected to identify genotypes with the highest lint yield.

The direct effect of DTE, SYM, NFFB and PLH on lint yield is negligible (near zero) (Table 5). Although BOP (-0.027) and BOW (-0.017) had negative direct effect on lint yield their contribution in explaining the variability in LHA was negligible. Seed cotton yield (83%) and GP (13%) explained almost all the variability in lint yield.

By selecting ginning percentage one cannot select indirectly other traits since it had negative or zero indirect effect on other variables. The total effect of ginning percentage on lint yield was positive (0.661) since ginning percentage had the highest positive indirect effect through seed cotton yield (0.395).

Boll number plant⁻¹ had second highest total effect on lint yield ha⁻¹ (0.926). By selecting boll number plant⁻¹ one can also select indirectly seed cotton yield (0.788). Its total effect on lint yield was high due to its indirect effect mainly through seed cotton yield but the direct effect of boll number plant⁻¹ on lint yield was negative (-

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0.027). By selecting hundred seed weight it is possible to select indirectly boll number plant⁻¹ (0.016). Its total effect on lint yield remained negative (-0.622) due to its negative indirect effect through other traits.

Generally, the traits that had highest positive total effect on lint yield were seed cotton yield (0.968), boll number (0.926), ginning percentage (0.661) and number of sympodial branches (0.572) and those had negative total effect were hundred seed weight (-0.622), boll weight (-0.463) and days to emergence (-0.342).

Table 5. Phenotypic direct and indirect effect of nine characters on lint yield ha⁻¹

Traits	DTE	SYM	NFFB	PLH	BOP	BOW	SHA	GP	HSW	LHA _{corr}
DTE	0.007	0.000	-0.001	0.001	0.007	-0.008	-0.276	-0.095	0.023	-0.342
SYM	-0.001	-0.000	0.001	-0.003	-0.017	0.000	0.548	0.053	-0.008	0.572
NFFB	-0.001	-0.000	0.007	-0.004	-0.012	0.006	0.269	0.141	-0.015	0.389
PLH	-0.001	-0.000	0.004	-0.008	-0.013	-0.002	0.353	-0.002	0.017	0.347
BOP	-0.002	-0.000	0.003	-0.004	-0.027	0.009	0.788	0.204	-0.044	0.926
BOW	0.003	0.000	-0.002	-0.001	0.013	-0.017	-0.259	-0.266	0.066	-0.463
SHA	-0.002	-0.000	0.002	-0.003	-0.024	0.005	0.872	0.152	-0.034	0.968
GP	-0.002	-0.000	0.003	0.000	-0.016	0.014	0.395	0.336	-0.068	0.661
HSW	0.002	0.000	-0.001	-0.002	0.016	-0.015	-0.392	-0.304	0.075	-0.622

Note that: Phenotypic direct effect (bold face) and phenotypic indirect effect of nine characters on lint yield/ha. For phenotypic: Coefficient of

determination (R²) = 0.999, residual effect = 0.001, DTE: Days to emergence, SYM: number of sympodial branch plant⁻¹, NFFB: number of nodes to

first fruiting branch, PLH: plant height (cm), BOP: boll plant⁻¹, BOW: boll weight (g), SHA: seed cotton yield ha⁻¹, GP: ginning percentage,

HSW: hundred seed weight (g), LHA_{corr}: lint yield ha⁻¹ correlation coefficient value

Importantly, the residual effects determine how the best the causal factors account for the variability of the dependent factor, i.e. lint yield ha⁻¹ and the residual effect was 0.1 % for the phenotypic coefficient of agronomic traits indicating that about 99.9% of the phenotypic total variation for agronomic traits was contributed by the nine characters included in the path analysis.

Therefore, the present study indicated that DTE, NFFB, SHA, GP, and HSW had positive direct effects on LHA.

Genotypic path coefficient for lint yield

A similar trend as in path coefficient analysis of the phenotypic correlations was observed in path coefficient analysis at the genotypic level. Except for SYM which had negative sign in phenotypic but positive sign in genotypic path coefficient analysis, the sign of the direct effects of each independent trait on lint yield was similar in both analyses. DTE, NFFB, SHA, GP and HSW had positive direct effects while PLH, BOP and BOW had negative direct effects on lint yield in both analyses. None of the direct effects were negligible in path analysis of genotypic correlations, the difference between them being narrower than those at the phenotypic level. They varied between -0.042 (DTE) to 0.783 (SHA). Although SHA (0.783) and GP (0.317) still had the highest positive direct effect on lint yield, now the direct effects of NFFB (0.119) and BOW (-0.112) are similar in absolute value to the direct effect of HSW (0.119). Still SHA (79%) and GP (13%) explained the bulk of the variability in lint yield at the genotypic level too. However the role of NFFB (1.8%), PLH (1.1%), BOW (1.6%) and HSW (1.8%) in explaining the variability of lint yield is higher than they were in path coefficient analysis of the phenotypic correlations. Here too the indirect effects of DTE, BOP, and HSW on lint yield via both SHA and GP is negative. SYM which had negative indirect effect on lint yield via both SHA and GP at phenotypic level had positive indirect effect via both traits at genotypic level. Plant height had negative indirect effect on

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lint yield via SHA but positive indirect effect on lint yield via GP at phenotypic level. At the genotypic level its indirect effect via both traits is negative. However the indirect effect of BOP (-0.092) on lint yield via SHA is now higher than that of HSW (-0.082). However HSW still had the largest indirect effect on lint yield via GP as at the phenotypic level. The indirect effects of SHA and GP on lint yield via each other is still the largest (0.224 and 0.553, respectively). Genotypes with highest SHA and GP are expected to produce high lint yield. However care should be taken not to select those with the tallest plants and having many bolls per plant and the largest seeds.

Backward elimination and forward selection methods of regression have both identified SHA, GP and HSW as the most influential variables that determine lint yield. These three traits explained 99.95% of the variability in lint yields while all nine quantitative traits explained 99.99% of this variability. SHA, GP and HSW alone explained almost all of the variability in lint yield. If we select four highest yielding lines by lint yield predicted from the regression that uses these three explanatory traits, the mean of the original population (all 16 genotypes) and the mean of these elite lines is given below in Table 6.

Table 6. Mean of 10 quantitative traits for all 16 genotypes and the four highest yielding lines

Traits	Mean of 16 Genotypes	Mean of 4 selected lines	Difference	Change in %
LHA	17.92	19.80	1.88	10.49
DTE	5.53	5.38	-0.17	-3.10
SYM	12.66	13.52	0.86	6.80
NFFB	5.08	5.21	0.13	2.60
PLH	102.57	112.24	9.67	9.40
BOP	14.92	17.37	2.45	16.40
BOW	5.21	5.19	-0.002	-0.38
SHA	45.36	49.96	4.60	10.14
GP	39.47	39.67	0.20	0.51
HSW	8.82	8.72	-0.10	-1.10

LHA: lint yield/ha, DTE: days to emergence, SYM: sympodial branch plant⁻¹, NFFB: number of nodes to first fruiting branch, PLH: plant height, BOP: boll number/plant⁻¹, BOW: boll weight, SHA: seed cotton yield ha⁻¹, GP: ginning percentage and HSW: hundred seed weight.

The mean DTE and HSW of the selected lines are lower than the mean of the original population as expected. The indirect effect of these two traits via SHA and GP was negative in both phenotypic and genotypic path analysis. Both traits also had negative correlation with LHA at both phenotypic and genotypic levels and a selection index designed to increase LHA will of course reduce the two traits.

Although the indirect effect of BOP via both SHA and GP was negative in both path coefficient analyses (phenotypic and genotypic), the mean of the selected lines was higher than the mean of the original population by 2.45 bolls plant⁻¹ (16.4%). This is because this trait had almost perfect positive correlation with LHA at both phenotypic and genotypic levels. It also had positive correlation with both SHA and GP. The negative indirect effects of this trait via both SHA and GP were also not large in absolute value. Therefore, an index that is designed to increase SHA, GP and LHA has also increased BOP.

As expected, the mean of the selected lines has increased by 10.14% in SHA, by 0.51% in GP and by 10.49% in LHA predicted from the regression equation.

Plant height has been increased by 9.4% although its indirect effect via both SHA and GP was negative. It had positive correlation with SHA, GP and LHA at both genotypic and phenotypic levels. This selection index has also increased SYM by 6.8% and NFFB by 2.6%. Simple linear regression of lint yield on each of the quantitative traits has also shown that SHA has explained 94.3% of LHA.

R² was higher than 1 (1.002) and the residual effect negative (-0.002) in path coefficient analysis of the genotypic correlations. This may be an indication that about 100% of the total variation in lint yield has been explained by the nine quantitative characters included in the path analysis of genotypic correlations.

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Results of phenotypic and genotypic path analysis obtained in this study agreed with the findings of Miller and Rawlings (1967) who found that seed cotton yield and ginning percent had high direct effect on lint yield of cotton.

Table 7. Genotypic direct and indirect effect of nine characters on lint yield ha⁻¹

Traits	DTE	SYM	NFFB	PLH	BOP	BOW	SHA	GP	HSW	LHAcorr
DTE	0.042	-0.008	-0.032	0.015	0.026	-0.077	-0.283	-0.136	0.051	-0.402
SYM	-0.007	0.049	0.030	-0.037	-0.061	0.011	0.755	0.088	-0.015	0.813
NFFB	-0.011	0.012	0.119	-0.074	-0.054	0.051	0.475	0.192	-0.034	0.677
PLH	-0.007	0.019	0.096	-0.093	-0.039	-0.002	0.237	0.035	0.029	0.276
BOP	-0.013	0.035	0.075	-0.042	-0.085	0.072	0.850	0.231	-0.081	1.042
BOW	0.029	-0.005	-0.054	-0.002	0.055	-0.112	-0.451	-0.282	0.111	-0.712
SHA	-0.015	0.047	0.072	-0.028	-0.092	0.064	0.783	0.224	-0.082	0.973
GP	-0.018	0.014	0.072	-0.010	-0.062	0.099	0.553	0.317	-0.116	0.850
HSW	0.018	-0.006	-0.034	-0.022	0.058	-0.104	-0.539	-0.308	0.119	-0.817

Note that: genotypic direct effect (bold face) and genotypic indirect effect of nine characters on lint yield kg/ha. For Genotypic: coefficient of determination (R²)=1.02, Residual effect = -0.02, DTE: Days to emergence, SYM:number of sympodial branch plant⁻¹, NFFB: number of nodes to first fruiting branch, PLH: plant height (cm), BOP: boll plant⁻¹, BOW: boll weight (g), SHA: seed cotton yield ha⁻¹ (kg), GP: ginning percentage, HSW: hundred seed weight(g), LHAcorr: lint yieldha⁻¹(kg).

The residual effect was 0 % for the genotypic coefficient of agronomic traits indicating that about 100% of the genotypic total variation for agronomic traits was contributed by the nine characters included in the path analysis. The residual effects determine how the best the causal factors account for the variability of the dependent factor, that is, lint yieldha⁻¹. Therefore, the present study indicated that number of sympodia branch; number of nodes to first fruiting branch, seed cotton yield ha⁻¹ and ginning percentage had positive direct effects on the lint yield ha⁻¹.

Fiber quality traits

Phenotypic path coefficient for fiber strength

Table 8 below shows phenotypic direct effect (bold face) and phenotypic indirect effect of 7 characters on fiber strength. Based on the results, UHML had showed the highest positive direct effect on fiber Strength (0.746). Although, the absolute value of SF (-0.082) and RD (-0.011) were nearly zero, they had negative phenotypic indirect effects on fiber strength via UHML. Lint yield (0.022), MIC(0.083), UNI (0.057), and RD (0.044), exhibited positive phenotypic indirect effects on fiber strength via UHM. The total effect of upper half mean length on fiber strength was 0.859. The direct effect of UHML, on fiber strength was higher than its indirect effect via other traits. The second trait which had the highest positive direct effect on fiber strength was SF (0.237), followed by length uniformity (0.094). On the contrary lint yield (-0.077), MIC (-0.118), RD (-0.460) and +b (-0.125) had negative direct impact on fiber strength. SF held negative total effect on fiber strength (-0.486) due to its negative or negligible indirect effect via other traits. SF had the highest negative indirect impact via degree of reflectance (-0.314), followed by UHML (-0.259). The third trait that had positive direct effect on fiber strength was UNI (0.094). Its total effect on fiber strength was 0.607 and positioned second next to UHML (0.859).

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Table 8. Phenotypic direct and indirect effect of 7 characters on fiber strength

Traits	LHA	MIC	UHML	UNI	SF	RD	+b	STRcorr
LHA	-0.077	-0.053	-0.211	-0.043	0.164	-0.307	-0.028	-0.555
MIC	-0.034	-0.118	-0.523	-0.032	0.095	-0.176	0.024	-0.763
UHML	0.022	0.083	0.746	0.057	-0.082	0.044	-0.011	0.859
UNI	0.035	0.040	0.457	0.094	-0.185	0.158	0.007	0.607
SF	-0.053	-0.048	-0.259	-0.073	0.237	-0.314	0.024	-0.486
RD	-0.051	-0.045	-0.071	-0.032	0.162	-0.460	0.017	-0.481
+b	-0.017	0.023	0.065	-0.005	-0.046	0.062	-0.125	-0.044

For phenotypic: Coefficient of determination = 0.942, residual effect = 0.058

LHA: lint yield ha⁻¹, MIC: micronaire, UHML: upper half mean length, UNI: length uniformity, SF: short fiber content, RD: degree of reflectance, +b: yellowness, STRcorr: fiber strength

Importantly, the residual effect was 5.8 % for the phenotypic coefficient of fiber quality traits (technological traits) indicating that 94.2% of the phenotypic total variation for fiber strength was contributed by the seven characters included in the path analysis. The residual effects determine how the best the causal factors account for the variability of the dependent factor, that is, fiber strength. Therefore, the present study indicated that UHML, UNI, and SF had positive direct effects on the fiber strength.

Genotypic path coefficient for fiber strength

Table 9 below presents the results obtained from the genotypic path analysis of fiber quality traits. Diagonally bolded values indicated the direct effects of traits on fiber strength. As the phenotypic path analysis, UHML (0.401) had exerted the highest genotypic positive direct effect on fiber strength. UNI and RD had positive direct genotypic effects on fiber strength, while LHA, MIC, SF and +b had exhibited negative direct effects on fiber strength. The negative direct effects of LHA, MIC, SF and +b on fiber strength indicated that those traits have harmful effects during selection process. The total effect of upper half mean length on fiber strength was 0.880.

Table 9. Genotypic direct and indirect effect of 7 characters on fiber strength

Traits	LHA	MIC	UHML	UNI	SF	RD	+b	STRcorr
LHA	-0.215	-0.229	-0.155	-0.083	-0.363	0.330	-0.010	-0.724
MIC	-0.143	-0.344	-0.322	-0.071	-0.193	0.207	0.004	-0.862
UHML	0.083	0.276	0.401	0.076	0.098	-0.052	-0.002	0.880
UNI	0.168	0.229	0.289	0.106	0.272	-0.209	0.003	0.859
SF	-0.256	-0.218	-0.129	-0.095	-0.305	0.417	0.007	-0.577
RD	-0.220	-0.219	-0.065	-0.068	-0.393	0.324	0.008	-0.634
+b	-0.088	0.058	0.036	-0.015	0.093	-0.102	-0.024	-0.042

Note that: Genotypic direct effect (bold face) and genotypic indirect effect of 7 characters on strength.

For genotypic: coefficient of determination=0.868, Residual effect = 0.132, LHA: lint yield ha⁻¹ (kg), MIC: micronaire, UHML: upper half mean length (mm), UNI: length uniformity (%), SF: short fiber content (%), RD: degree of reflectance, +b: yellowness, STRcorr: fiber strength (gram/tex)

The residual effect was 13.2% for the genotypic coefficient of fiber quality traits (technological traits) indicating that 86.8% of the genotypic total variation for fiber quality were contributed by the seven characters included in the path analysis. The residual effects determine how the best the causal factors account for the variability of the dependent factor, that is, fiber strength. Therefore, the present study indicated that upper half mean length, fiber length uniformity and degree of reflectance had positive direct effects on the fiber strength.

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Generally, based on the phenotypic and genotypic path analysis results obtained from the agronomic traits which showed positive direct effects on lint yield were: number of sympodial branch, number of nodes to first fruiting branch, seed cotton yield ha⁻¹ and ginning percentage. This result agrees with that of Miller and Rawlings (1967). Similarly the phenotypic and genotypic path analysis result obtained from the fiber quality traits that showed positive direct effects on fiber strength were upper half mean length, and fiber length uniformity.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study of associations among various traits at genotypic and phenotypic level showed that lint yield ha⁻¹ was positively associated with number of sympodial branches, plant height, number of nodes to first fruiting branch, boll number plant⁻¹, seed cotton yield ha⁻¹, ginning percentage, short fiber content and degree of reflectance, micronaire and yellowness with lint yield, which is considerably significant to breeder because component breeding would be very effective under such situation. Lint yield had negative association with days to emergence, boll weight, hundred seed weight, upper half mean length and strength at both phenotypic and genotypic level.

The path coefficient analysis at phenotypic and genotypic level for agronomic traits revealed that seed cotton yield ha⁻¹ and ginning percentage were the most important traits in determining lint yield ha⁻¹. These traits exhibited positive direct effect on lint yield.

The residual effect for path analysis of agronomic traits at phenotypic as well as genotypic level was zero indicating that the major variability in lint yield ha⁻¹ was accounted for by 9 traits included in the present study.

The path coefficient analysis of quality traits at phenotypic level revealed that upper half mean length had showed the highest direct positive effect on fiber strength followed by short fiber content, respectively. These traits were the most important in determining fiber strength and had beneficial role on it. The residual effect for path analysis at phenotypic level was 0.058 for fiber quality traits indicating that the major variability in fiber strength was accounted for by 7 traits included in the present study.

The path coefficient analysis at genotypic level for fiber quality traits had showed upper half mean length, and degree of reflectance had positive direct effect on fiber strength. The residual effect for path analysis of fiber quality traits (technological traits) at genotypic level was 0.132 indicating that the major variability in fiber strength was accounted for by 7 traits included in the present study.

In conclusion, the present study has highlighted the existence of weak to strong associations for the traits under study of upland cotton.

However, selection criteria suggested by correlation and path analysis studies needs to be confirmed by further studies over years and locations to use it in developing cultivars suitable to varied environmental conditions.

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